

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Stability Estimation of the Problem of Integral Geometry on a Family of Parabolas

N.U.Uteuliev¹, G.Djaykov¹, A.K.Seidullaev²

¹*Nukus state technical university, Nukus, Uzbekistan*

²*Karakalpak State University, Nukus, Uzbekistan*

Introduction. The papers [1,2,3] investigate weakly ill-posed integral geometry problems involving families of parabolas. Theorems regarding the existence, uniqueness, and stability of solutions were established, and conversion formulas were derived [4,5].

Radon's seminal work [6] forms the foundation of the theory of integral geometry problems [7], which underpins various applications in imaging [8], seismology [9] and numerous other fields.

This paper [10] addresses integral geometry problems involving a family of parabolas and derives an approximate regularized sequential conversion formula. The current work builds on this, focusing on estimating the error in the space using the derived conversion formula. To validate the results, several test examples with numerical solutions are provided.

Statement of the problem 1: Reconstruct the function of two variables $u(x, y)$ within the strip $L_H = (x, y) : x \in R^1, 0 \leq \eta \leq y \leq H$ if its integrals over the curves in the family $Y(x, y)$ are known

$$\int_{Y(x,y)} u(\xi, \eta) d\xi = f(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where the expression describes any curve from the family

$$Y(x, y) = (\xi, \eta) : x - \xi = \sqrt{y - \eta}, \quad 0 \leq \eta \leq y$$

Statement of the problem 2: Within the region $\Omega_H = (x, y) : x \in R^1, y \leq \eta \leq H$ reconstruct the function of two variables $u(x, y)$ if the integrals of this function along the curves in the family $\Lambda(x, y)$ are known

$$\int_{\Lambda(x,y)} u(\xi, \eta) d\xi = f(x, y) \quad (2)$$

where the expression gives any curve from the family

$$\Lambda(x, y) = (\xi, \eta) : x - \xi = \sqrt{\eta - y}, \quad y \leq \eta \leq H$$

For these two problems, we have the following lemmas. The proofs of these lemmas can be found in [10].

Lemma 1. Consider a function $f(x, y)$ known within the strip L_H . Then the solution of equation (1) in the class of C^2 finite functions, which have support in the strip L_H , is unique and can be represented as

$$\hat{u}(\lambda, y) = \frac{\partial}{\pi \partial y} \int_0^y \frac{ch(\lambda \sqrt{y-\eta})}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} \hat{f}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{u}(\lambda, y)$ and $\hat{f}(\lambda, y)$ represent the Fourier transform of the first variable applied to the functions $u(x, y)$ and $f(x, y)$, respectively. Lemma 2. Let $f(x, y)$ be a function twice continuously differentiable concerning its arguments and finite within the domain Ω . The unique solution of the equation (2), which is also twice continuously differentiable and has a finite value, can be expressed as:

$$\hat{u}(\lambda, y) = -\frac{\partial}{\pi \partial y} \int_y^H \frac{ch(\lambda \sqrt{\eta-y})}{\sqrt{\eta-y}} \hat{f}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{u}(\lambda, y)$ and $\hat{f}(\lambda, y)$ represent the Fourier transform of the first variable applied to the functions $u(x, y)$ and $f(x, y)$, respectively.

Theorem 1. Let the function $f(x, y)$ be defined in the domain L_H . We consider the regularizing operator for equation (3), which is given by:

$$R(u, \alpha) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}[\hat{u}e^{-\alpha_1^2 \lambda^2}]$$

Then, on the rectangle L_H with support $\overline{L_H}$, Problem 1 in the class of twice continuously differentiable, finite functions gives the following solution:

$$u_{\alpha_1}(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\alpha_1 \sqrt{\pi^3}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^y \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{y-\eta-(x-\xi)^2}{4\alpha_1^2}} \cos \frac{(x-\xi)\sqrt{y-\eta}}{2\alpha_1^2} \frac{f(\xi, \eta)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} d\xi d\eta$$

and satisfies the following inequality:

$$\|u_{\alpha_1} - u\|_{L_2(\overline{L_H})} \leq C_1 \alpha_1^2 \|f\|_{L_2(\overline{L_H})}$$

where $\alpha_1 > 0$ is a regularization parameter, \mathcal{F}^{-1} is the inverse Fourier transform, and C_1 is a positive constant.

Theorem 2. Let the function $f(x, y)$ be defined within the domain Ω . We examine the regularization operator for equation (4).

$$R(u, \alpha) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}[\hat{u}e^{-\alpha_1^2 \lambda^2}]$$

Thus, the solution to Problem 2, in the class of twice continuously differentiable, finite functions with support in the rectangle Ω , is represented as follows:

$$u_{\alpha_2}(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\alpha_2 \sqrt{\pi^3}} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_y^H \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{\eta-y-(x-\xi)^2}{4\alpha_2^2}} \cos \frac{(x-\xi)\sqrt{\eta-y}}{2\alpha_2^2} \frac{f(\xi, \eta)}{\sqrt{\eta-y}} d\xi d\eta$$

and the inequality holds true

$$\|u_{\alpha_2} - u\|_{L_2(\hat{\Omega})} \leq C_2 \alpha_2^2 \|f\|_{L_2(\hat{\Omega})}$$

where α_2 is a positive regularization parameter, \mathcal{F}^{-1} is the inverse Fourier transform, and C_2 is a positive constant.

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